

PENGUIN: An Interactive Knowledge Graph Platform for Cross-Platform Discovery of Polar Research Records

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Abstract. PENGUIN is a web application built on the Polar Science Knowledge Graph (PSKG) for discovering polar research records distributed across databases and platforms and for understanding why they are scientifically related. Rather than treating discovery as a static result list, PENGUIN represents source-derived records and scientific entities as interconnected nodes in an interactive graph workspace, with typed relations represented as edges. Users can progressively expand neighboring nodes, inspect explicit relation paths, and follow links to authoritative source records or supporting evidence. PENGUIN also supports AI-assisted exploration, in which a natural-language scientific question is used to construct a relevant subgraph from PSKG-derived candidates. By preserving links to original sources while exposing the scientific context connecting records, PENGUIN acts as a bridge for explainable cross-platform data discovery. This demo presents the interface and representative exploration workflows.

Keywords: Knowledge graphs · Polar science · AI-assisted exploration · Graph-based data discovery · Cross-platform discovery

1 Introduction

Polar research relies on research records distributed across data platforms, domain-specific databases, archives, and non-database research materials. Previous efforts have supported cross-repository discovery in the polar community through federated search [6, 8] and improved concept-based findability through semantic annotation of research data [1]. These approaches help users locate resources, but they do not, on their own, provide inspectable relation paths

that show why particular records from different sources are scientifically related. Knowledge graphs provide a complementary means of representing entities and their relations in an explicit and interconnected form [2]. Our companion work introduces the Polar Science Knowledge Graph (PSKG) for relation-centered discovery across polar research resources [9]. The PSKG represents traceable source-derived records as data-layer nodes and links them to reusable scientific entities and concepts through typed relations. It thereby makes scientific connections among records explicit while preserving their source context and traceability.

PENGUIN (Platform for Exploring Network Graphs of Unified Interdisciplinary Notions) operationalizes the PSKG through a web-based interface. It offers three entry routes into the same shared graph workspace: keyword-based search for known terms or record attributes, AI-assisted exploration from natural-language research questions, and direct entry from records hosted by connected external platforms. From any visible node, users can expand the surrounding graph to add neighboring nodes and typed relations, inspect the relation paths through which related records are connected, and navigate to supporting evidence or authoritative source records. The companion work describes the complete PSKG data model and construction workflow; this paper focuses on how PENGUIN turns that infrastructure into a practical environment for exploring polar research records and their scientific context.

2 Overview of the PENGUIN Platform

PENGUIN provides researchers and data managers in polar science and related fields with a web-based interface for accessing and exploring the PSKG. Figure 1 shows the home page and main workspace. The home page lists the principal node types currently represented in the PSKG, giving users an initial overview of the available content. The *Open workspace* button launches the interactive graph workspace.

The main workspace combines search and AI-assisted exploration modules with a shared graph workspace. The workspace maintains the visible sub-graph assembled during the current session. Links from connected external platforms can also open the PENGUIN workspace with the corresponding data-layer node already loaded. Knowledge-layer entities are shown as blue circular nodes, data-layer records as green rounded rectangles, and edges are labeled with relation types. Users can inspect, remove, expand, and download the assembled subgraph for later use. The current implementation is available at <https://penguin.nipr.ac.jp/>.

3 Demonstration Scenarios

The following scenarios demonstrate how PENGUIN supports progressive, source-traceable graph exploration. Users begin from a record, term, or research

Fig. 1. Overview of the PENGUIN interface. (a) The home page presents the principal research-record and knowledge-entity types represented in the PSKG. (b) The main workspace contains the AI-assisted exploration module, the search module, and the shared graph workspace.

question; expand the surrounding graph; inspect explicit relation paths and supporting sources; and discover related records across platforms.

3.1 Keyword-Based Entry and Manual Graph Exploration

For users who know a relevant term or record attribute, manual search provides the keyword-based entry route. The workflow combines three core interactions: locating a seed node, expanding its graph neighborhood, and inspecting graph elements and their supporting information.

Users can combine keywords with optional ranges for date and time, latitude, longitude, altitude, and depth. After a query is submitted, the search results panel displays candidate nodes. Selecting a result adds the corresponding node to the graph workspace as an entry point for further exploration (Figure 2).

Once a seed node is visible, the user can invoke *Explore* to retrieve adjacent nodes. Because a node may have many neighbors, PENGUIN groups candidates by relation type and displays the number available in each group. The user can select a relation type, review the associated candidates, and add chosen nodes together with their connecting relations (Figure 3). Repeating this process progressively extends the visible subgraph, allowing users to discover related records together with the typed relations and intermediate entities that connect them, rather than replacing the current view with a new result list.

Users can double-click any visible node or relation to inspect its properties and supporting information. For a data-layer node, the source URL normally points to the corresponding record page on its authoritative platform. For a

Fig. 2. Keyword-based entry in PENGUIN. (a) The user specifies a keyword and optional date/time, latitude, longitude, altitude, and depth filters. (b) The search module returns candidate nodes. (c) A selected node is added to the graph workspace as the exploration seed.

Fig. 3. Progressive graph-neighborhood expansion. (a) The user invokes *Explore* on a visible node. (b) Neighboring nodes are grouped by relation type. (c) The user reviews candidates in a selected group. (d) A chosen node and its connecting relation are added to the workspace.

knowledge-layer node or relation, an evidence URL may instead identify an external reference supporting the represented entity, concept, or scientific relation. Figure 4 shows an atmospheric-observation data-layer node representing surface air temperature observations along the Dome Fuji route. Its source URL points to the corresponding metadata record in the NIPR Science Database, which serves as the authoritative source platform in this example [3].

Fig. 4. Inspection of a data-layer node and navigation to its source record. (a) The detail panel displays node properties and a source URL. (b) Following the URL opens the corresponding record page on its authoritative source platform, which in this example is the NIPR Science Database. Knowledge-layer nodes and relations may likewise include links to supporting references where available.

3.2 Natural-Language Entry through AI-Assisted Exploration

Researchers may begin with a scientific question without knowing the keywords, domain terminology, classification schemes, or record types used by relevant data sources. Research on data discovery has likewise emphasized the need for repository interfaces to account for users’ search contexts and diverse search behaviors [7]. To support question-driven and interdisciplinary discovery, PENGUIN allows users to enter the workspace by expressing a research question in natural language.

After a question is submitted to the AI-assisted exploration module, the system expands the graph step by step. At each step, the backend supplies the language model with the question, a summary of the current workspace subgraph, and candidate graph elements derived from the PSKG. The model selects a promising exploration direction from these candidates, after which the backend retrieves the corresponding nodes and relations. An exploration log displays the process and allows the user to pause it.

The workflow first identifies relevant knowledge-layer entities and expands their relations to construct a contextual subgraph. It then continues from selected knowledge-layer entities to connected data-layer records. Figure 5 shows this process for a question concerning algal productivity and Antarctic coastal food webs.

The language model neither invents graph elements nor provides an uninspectable final answer. All nodes and relations added during the process are retrieved from the PSKG and remain visible for inspection. Users can examine connection paths and supporting sources, remove elements, and continue manually from the resulting subgraph. PENGUIN therefore uses the language model

Fig. 6. Cross-platform discovery through PENGUIN. (a) A record in the Southern Ocean Zooplankton Monitoring Database (Platform A) provides a PENGUIN link. (b) The corresponding data-layer node is loaded as the workspace entry point. (c) Graph expansion through related knowledge-layer entities and typed relations reveals a hydrozoan specimen record. (d) Following the discovered node’s source URL opens the authoritative record on AMIDER (Platform B).

Figure 6 demonstrates the complete pathway. Starting from a record in the Southern Ocean Zooplankton Monitoring Database [5], the user enters PENGUIN at the corresponding data-layer node, follows a graph path through Hydrozoa-related knowledge-layer entities to a specimen record, and then opens the corresponding authoritative record on AMIDER [4]. This platform-to-PENGUIN-to-platform pathway supports cross-platform discovery without requiring participating systems to transfer records to a central repository or adopt a common internal schema.

4 Conclusion

This paper presented PENGUIN, a web application that operationalizes the PSKG as an interactive graph workspace for discovering polar research records distributed across databases and platforms. Rather than replacing source plat-

forms or returning a static result list, PENGUIN exposes source-derived records, knowledge-layer entities, and typed relations so that users can expand the graph, inspect relation paths, and follow links to authoritative source records or supporting evidence. The demonstrated workflows support keyword-based entry, PSKG-grounded AI-assisted exploration from natural-language questions, and platform-to-PENGUIN-to-platform discovery. This design enables explainable cross-platform discovery while preserving the authority and independence of the original systems.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Strategic Research Projects program of the Research Organization of Information and Systems (ROIS).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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